

Emotional Intelligence as Predictor of Academic Success among Third Year College Students of PIT

Sonia Arradaza-Pajaron

Abstract—College students are expected to engage in an on-the-job training or internship for completion of a course requirement prior to graduation. In this scenario, they are exposed to the real world of work outside their training institution. To find out their readiness both emotionally and academically, this study has been conducted. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed and random sampling technique method was utilized among 265 randomly selected third year college students of PIT, SY 2014-15.

A questionnaire on Emotional Intelligence (bearing the four components namely; emotional literacy, emotional quotient competence, values and beliefs and emotional quotient outcomes) was fielded to the respondents and GWA was extracted from the school automate. Data collected were statistically treated using percentage, weighted mean and Pearson-r for correlation.

Results revealed that respondents' emotional intelligence level is moderately high while their academic performance is good. A high significant relationship was found between the EI component; Emotional Literacy and their academic performance while only significant relationship was found between Emotional Quotient Outcomes and their academic performance. Therefore, if EI influences academic performance significantly when correlated, a possibility that their OJT performance can also be affected either positively or negatively. Thus, EI can be considered predictor of their academic and academic-related performance. Based on the result, it is then recommended that the institution would try to look deeply into the consideration of embedding emotional intelligence as part of the (especially on Emotional Literacy and Emotional Quotient Outcomes of the students) college curriculum. It can be done if the school shall have an effective Emotional Intelligence framework or program manned by qualified and competent teachers, guidance counselors in different colleges in its implementation.

Keywords—Academic performance, emotional intelligence, emotional literacy, emotional quotient competence, emotional quotient outcomes, values and beliefs.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE landscape of development for every child in school does not only refer to the cognitive aspects or IQ alone. Traditionally, schools have concentrated on enhancing students' cognitive abilities but developing them to be emotional smart is just as vital. These students are trained and educated in school with one main objective, their success in the future. What is then the true measure of success? Is it a strong scientific mind only?

Reference [2] mentioned that learners to be encouraged in developing their full potential in everything they do, must have a seemingly valuable consideration of their emotional

intelligence not only their mental capacity alone [1], [2]. He added that the four common domains of EI namely; self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and relational management have to be developed to have a higher level of emotional intelligence [1].

Emotional Intelligence is a type of social intelligence that involves the ability to monitor one's own and other's feelings and emotion that discriminate among them and to use the information to guide one's own thinking and action [2]. Similarly, 'intrapersonal' and 'interpersonal' intelligences are just as important as intelligences measured by IQ and other tests because these affect how one emotionally responds to situations and cognitive understanding, thus, closely related to emotional intelligence [7]. If facilitated properly, it might have a significant impact in the total development of a person, not only influence academic performance while still in school.

Academic performance is an output of knowledge attained and developed in the school subjects manifested in their grades (GWA). It is the level of actual accomplishment of proficiency one has achieved in academic area, further, considered as the articulation of a student's performance measured through their grades [3]. Premised by these concepts, this study tried at determining the relationship between emotional intelligence (including its domains) and academic performance and investigated further whether it can be a possible predictor of academic success among the respondents. Reference [4] added that emotional intelligence as a different way of being smart, it is being able to manage stress well and control impulses, being motivated and hopeful when one has setbacks in working towards achieving a goal. Unlike academic achievement, it is an important intangible factor of a student's performance in school since it is the ability to adjust, adapt, understand and handle situations especially in facing predicaments and tasks too important to leave to mental intellect alone. In other words, it is the capacity for recognizing one's own feelings and those of others, for motivating oneself, and for managing emotions well of oneself and others.

Among college students, one of the curricular requirements prior to graduation is their deployment to various industries, agencies or academic institutions for their on-the-job training, practice teaching, and shipboard training. It's just wise enough for academic training institution, like Palompon Institute of Technology, to ensure the readiness of these college students, academically, technically, and emotionally, as they venture the outside world. Their exposure to the real and unstructured world means vastness of work-related challenges, adjustment to current environment and most of all, interpersonal relation.

S. A. Pajaron is with the Palompon Institute of Technology, Evangelista St., 6538 Palompon, Leyte, Phils. Philippines (phone: 053-338-4884; fax: 053-555-9841; e-mail: sonpaj5671@yahoo.com).

The need to manage and cope with situations to withstand the pressures relative to interfacing with co-workers is deemed important. As emotional intelligence is not only a part of student life or on the world of education, it is also becoming a significant factor of one's recruitment in corporate life and in social life too, which is beyond his academic achievement [5]. Therefore, if emotional intelligence is considered vital for success that affects students' academic achievement, it might be imperative for academic training institutions to envision a possible intervention to develop it among students, like integrating it in the curricular program or conducting trainings or training relative to its enhancement. In this way, total development and well-being of every student while in the academic training institution, personality enhancement and values inculcation shall be facilitated early on. These are also too significant as they face life's complexities when they leave the portals of the institution and meet the real world.

In PIT, there is no integration of lessons or subject in the college curricula relative to emotional intelligence, thus, the researcher investigated the possible association between emotional intelligence and academic performance among third year college students. Further, investigate the possible influence of such relationship can be manifested in their on-the-job training performance, thus, can be considered as a predictor of their academic success.

A. Framework of the Study

This study is inspired and anchored on the studies of [10] and [1] who assert that emotional intelligence, as a psychological theory, is the ability to perceive emotions, to access and generate emotions so as to assist thought, to understand emotions and emotional knowledge, and to reflectively regulate emotions so as to promote emotional and intellectual growth [1], [10]. In fact, [1] defines emotional 'competence' as "a learned capability based on emotional intelligence that results in outstanding performance at work", that it represents our potential for achieving mastery of specific abilities in this domain. The emotional competencies themselves represent the degree to which an individual has mastered specific, skills and abilities that build on EI and allow them greater effectiveness in the workplace.

He added that the basic view of emotional intelligence is that emotions aren't necessarily the opposite of thinking, but a different way of thinking about different types of problems that exist in our world. In fact, the latter arguably mentioned the four pillars/domains of EI that need to be facilitated to develop a better or high emotional intelligence level. These are self-awareness, self-management, social awareness and relational management. These four pillars/domains guided this study to pattern the various components in the instrument fielded to the identified respondents. Further, the study would provide a cleared perspective of the EI component/s which the respondents' need to be developed and facilitated to enhance Emotional Intelligence, thus, focused and appropriate intervention measure can be done while in PIT for them to have better performance in their OJT.

Fig. 1 Conceptual Framework of the Study

B. Statement of the Problem

The main purpose of this study was to look into the emotional intelligence level and academic performance of the third year college students who shall have their on-the-job training (OJT) the following year. It also investigated on the relationship that exist between emotional intelligence (components) and academic performance and looked into the possibility of EI as predictor of their academic performance. Specifically, the study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the level of emotional intelligence of the third year college students of SY 2013-14?
2. What is the level of academic performance of the students based on their General Weighted Average (GWA)?
3. Which among the domains of emotional intelligence (as represented in the instrument of the study) manifested significant relationship with the students' academic performance?
 - 3.1. Emotional Literacy
 - 3.2. Emotional Quotient Competence
 - 3.3. Values & Beliefs
 - 3.4. Emotional Quotient Outcomes?
4. Is there a significant relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Academic performance?
5. Is Emotional Intelligence a predictor of academic success among third year college students?

C. Hypothesis

1. There is a significant relationship between academic performance and emotional intelligence among third year college students in the four identified components/domains;
 - a. emotional literacy
 - b. emotional quotient competence
 - c. values & beliefs
 - d. emotional quotient outcomes.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive-correlational method to determine the relationship between emotional intelligence and academic performance of the third year college students, as well as, the relationship that exist in the EI components correlated with their academic performance.

B. Sampling Technique

Purposive sampling technique was employed to come up with the actual respondents since the respondents considered in the study were 50% or one half of the total population per course of the officially enrolled third year college students of SY 2014-15 who shall have their on-the-job training the following school year. They were the group of third year college students who answered the personal survey questionnaire which was then considered the basis for the extraction of general weighted average (first to third year) from the school automate.

TABLE I
 RESPONDENTS OF THE STUDY

Undergrad Students	n	%
COTE	72	27.17
CAS	65	24.53
CoEd	45	16.98
CoMED	83	31.32
Total	265	100

There are seventy two (72) students or 27.17% from the College of Technology and Engineering were selected from the three curricular programs, namely; thirty (30) from Bachelor of Science in Industrial Technology or BSIT, twenty two (22) from Bachelor of Science in Information Technology and twenty (20) from the Mechanical and Industrial Engineering courses.

On the other hand, the College of Arts and Sciences had a total of sixty five (65) respondents 24.53% broken down as follows; twenty five students (25) Bachelor of Science in Shipping Management, thirty (30) form Bachelor of Science in Hotel and Restaurant Management and only ten (10) from the AB Communication. The next group of group of respondents were those that belong to the College of Education, namely; fourteen (14) were Bachelor of Secondary Education, fifteen (15) were Bachelor in Elementary Education and finally sixteen (16) were students in the Home Technology Education program. In summary, a total of forty five (45) or 16.98% of pre-service teachers were involved in the study.

Lastly, the final group of respondents are from the College of Maritime education students consisting of forty (40) from Nautical Science while forty two (42) from Marine Engineering course, respectively, over-all it tallied to eighty three (83) or 31.32% of the students came from this college.

The above data provided a grand total of 265 third year college student considered as actual respondents. Of the total population of 575 third year college students, only 265 of them were able to actually fill out personal survey questionnaires on emotional intelligence because some of them either came in very late to the class or were actually absent. Prior to the conduct of the study, an approved letter-request was sought from the vice president for academic affairs. Upon its approval, the researcher immediately fielded the EI questionnaire and retrieval of their general weighted average from the registrar's office automate followed.

C. Research Instrument

1. Emotional Intelligence

The instrument used was the Emotional Intelligence Survey Questionnaire adapted from the study of [2] consisting of four sections namely; Sec.1- Emotional Literacy (75 items)- deals with self-awareness of oneself and others, Sec. 2- Emotional Quotient Competence – (125 items)-deals with how he/she manages and controls internal and external pressures, Sec.3- Values & Beliefs (150 items)- is about measure inner strength and emotional disposition, and Sec.4-Emotional Quotient Outcomes (125 items) –measure the total emotional condition of the respondents from physical and interpersonal relationship [2].

2. Academic Performance

Data were extracted from the school automate after permission from the vice president has been sought and sent to the deans of every college.

Data were collected, tabulated and computed statistically thru Microsoft Excel program. Percentage mean was employed in determining the level of emotional intelligence while average mean for academic performance. Percentage and Mean (Data were subjected to Microsoft Excel) were employed to determine the emotional intelligence level, academic performance and relationship, respectively. While Pearson (*r*) moment coefficient correlation was utilized to look into the relationship between variables using their individual EI average mean against their general weighted average. This study utilized the descriptive-correlational method to determine the relationship between emotional intelligence and academic performance of the third year college students as well as the significant relationship that exist between variables [6].

III. RESEARCH FINDING

People in the corporate world have been trying to embrace the concept of Emotional Intelligence as predictor of worker's success. In the academe, fewer are showing concern to dig into a study of this intangible yet potent predictor for academic success.

Reference [2] discussed the four pillars or dimensions in her Emotional Intelligence study which are self-awareness, social awareness, self-regulation / management and interpersonal / relationship management [1], [2]. Accordingly, one needs to recognize and develop the first pillar (self-awareness) first before one can facilitate the other three pillars or dimensions to fully develop emotional intelligence.

Table II illustrates in plurality the respondents' emotional intelligence level based on the identified EI components considered in this particular study. They had *emotional quotient competence* as the lowest among the four EI components which implies that they may not be that adept into management and regulation of their emotion as they deal with people around them. This might be because of the notion that these students were either the non-passers or low scorers in the entrance test during their freshmen year especially among the

BSIT and BS Info. Tech. students. Moreover, they are more accustomed to technical or hands-on skilled activities in laboratory shops than hone their social/relational skills outside the classroom. Another very important feature is their grading system which is based on a 40% passing percentage in all subjects which is lower than 10% compared to CAS and CoEd and 20% by CoMed, respectively.

TABLE II
EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE LEVEL OF THE THIRD YEAR COLLEGE STUDENTS

Respondents	EI Components	% mean per component	Ave. % Mean (per group)	Interpretation
COTE	Emotional Literacy*	70.87	70.54	moderate EI
	Emotional Quotient Competence	68.92		
	Values & Beliefs	71.36		
	Emotional Quotient Outcomes	71.00		
CAS	Emotional Literacy*	74.82	77.80	high EI
	Emotional Quotient Competence	77.09		
	Values & Beliefs	80.47		
	Emotional Quotient Outcomes	79.61		
CoEd	Emotional Literacy*	70.70	74.40	moderate EI
	Emotional Quotient Outcomes	73.88		
	Values & Beliefs	77.59		
	Emotional Quotient Outcomes	75.44		
CoMed	Emotional Literacy*	71.35	75.00	high EI
	Emotional Quotient Outcomes	74.34		
	Values & Beliefs	76.29		
	Emotional Quotient Outcomes	77.82		
Grand Total			74.45	moderate EI

Categorical Description

88.00 - 100.00 – Very High Emotional Intelligence,
75.00 - 87.99 - High Emotional Intelligence,
62.00 - 74.9 – Moderate Emotional intelligence,
50.00 – 61.99 - Less Emotional Intelligence,
49.99 and below -Very Low Emotional Intelligence

Student-respondents from the College of Technology and Eng'g are categorized to have high level of values and beliefs yet seemed they still lack self-awareness and facilitation of such emotion to aid them in their self-regulation and self-management, thus, resulted to a low emotional competence

level. The second group, are the students from the College of Arts and Science which yielded an average mean of 77.80%, considered as the highest among the group and categorized with high emotional intelligence level. Notably, they acquired high percentage in *values and beliefs* component (80.47%) and lowest in *emotional literacy* (74.82%). While among the pre-service teachers of the College of Education, the average percentage mean is 74.40% categorized as moderate emotional intelligence level. The highest average mean of the entire group is on the component *values and beliefs* (77.59%) and the lowest is on *emotional literacy* (70.70%). Although both group of respondents vary a little in average percentages and means, they exactly had the same high and low category among the four components. This group might have better values and beliefs yet have not recognized them as factors to enhance fully their emotional intelligence. This female dominated group especially in CAS, that offers courses in business management-related (BSSM), communications (ABCom) and people oriented (BSHRM), still need to develop a real sense of emotional intelligence to really brace them in some challenging situation in their on-the-job training which need emotional firmness. Likewise, the pre-service teachers of CoEd, who shall equip themselves with tons of skills to fulfill their practice teaching tasks, like the communicating, disciplining and managing classroom assessment. It is sufficient to conclude that there is self-awareness in the person.

Table III depicts the emotional intelligence level of the entire group of respondents based on the identified EI dimensions. Data yielded that CAS has the highest emotional intelligence level among the four colleges, followed by CoMed, then CoEd and lastly CoTE, as the lowest. Based on the data presented, the lowest percentage they all have is on *emotional literacy* (71.82%) while the highest in on *values and beliefs* while their grand mean (74.45%) is considered as *moderate emotional intelligence* level.

The data gathered imply that respondents may have the inner strength and better emotional disposition as manifested in their high ratings in values and belief components yet lack the recognition of these emotions and may not be fully aware on how they can utilize these to show their true emotional expression, especially in managing or facing situation in their day-to-day interfacing with people.

TABLE III
SUMMARY TABLE OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE LEVEL OF THE RESPONDENTS IN THE FOUR EI COMPONENTS

EI Components	Respondents(per College)				Ave.	Interpretation
	CoTE	CAS	CoEd	CoMed		
Emotional Literacy	70.87	74.82	70.70	70.87	71.82	Moderate EI
Emotional Quotient Competence	68.92	77.09	73.88	74.34	73.56	Moderate EI
Values & Beliefs	71.36	80.47	77.59	76.29	76.43	High EI
Emotional Quotient Outcomes	71.00	79.61	75.44	77.82	75.99	High EI
Overall Average	70.54	77.80	74.40	75.00	74.45	Moderate EI

Categorical Description

88.00 - 100.00 - Very High Emotional Intelligence,
75.00 - 87.99 - High Emotional Intelligence,
62.00 - 74.9 - Moderate Emotional intelligence,
50.00 – 61.99 - Less Emotional Intelligence,
49.99 and below -Very Low Emotional Intelligence

A. Academic Performance of the Respondents

Academic performance is the result of the sum total participation of students in all the academic subjects and academic-related activities needed to be done in school; it can be either formative or summative in nature.

Table IV illustrates the academic performance of the respondents based on their general weighted average from first year to third year college. Among the four groups, the highest average grade is 1.99 from the respondents of the College of Education, followed by the College of Technology and Engineering with 2.11, then College of Arts and Sciences with 2.19, lastly, the College of Maritime Education having an average grade of 2.29. The CoTE respondents might have played second compared with other groups because their basis for rating/grading is only at 40% the passing percentage. In addition, the Mechanical/Industrial Eng'g. students yielded a better average grade among the three other group of students from other curricular programs in this college. This literally pulled their grades up to come up with that weighted average grade of the entire college.

TABLE IV
LEVEL OF ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF THE RESPONDENTS

Undergrad Colleges	n	Level of AP	Rank	Interpretation
College of Technology & Eng'g				
➤ BSIT	30	2.17		
➤ BSInfo. Tech.	22	2.12		
➤ BSME/BSIEng'g.	20	2.04	2	Good
Average	72	2.11		
College of Arts & Sciences				
➤ BSSM	25	2.29		
➤ BSHRM	30	2.18	3	Good
➤ ABCom	10	2.10		
Average	65	2.19		
College of Education				
➤ BSEd	14	1.90		
➤ BEEd	15	2.03	1	Good
➤ BSHTe	16	2.05		
Average	45	1.99		
College of Maritime Education				
➤ Marine Transportation	41	2.09		
➤ Marine Engineering	42	2.49	4	Good
Average	83	2.29		
Total	265	2.16		Good

GWA Range and Description
1.00 – Outstanding/Excellent **3.41- 4.20** - Conditional
1.01- 1.8 – Very Good **4.21- 5.0** - Failed
1.81-2.60 – Good

Following the COTE group are the respondents from the College of Arts and Sciences composed of three groups under three curricular programs similar with CoTE and CoEd. Clearly, it is the ABCom group that manifested a better average grade even though they are just very few in this college. Although this course has only one section with 22 students yet they displayed a better academic performance based on their average grade compared with other students from other courses in the college. Probably, one of the reasons is their being more vocal and less ashamed to communicate

with people around them because that is how they are trained as Communication students.

The next group is composed of students considered as the pre-service teachers having the highest average grade in the entire group of respondents. Their average mean grade is 1.99 with the BSEd leading them. These BSEd students are those with specialized academic subjects. They are the group who seemed to be so concerned over their performance, in fact, conscious with their grades. Usually, students with latin honors are coming from them, furthermore, they are also the same group tasked to conduct or facilitate activities in the college and some of them are even student leaders in the campus.

Finally, the CoMed students composed of only two groups got an average grade of 2.29 with a little difference of .40. In this college, students are rated based on a 60% passing percentage rating in all subject areas. Like the CoEd, these students are truly conscious and focused on their academic performance because of the various qualifying assessment they need to go through before they can be accommodated for ship board training with Dutch fleets.

Aside from a good academic standing, they have to pass the KVNR examinations given towards the end of their third year level prior to the selection of ship owners for the actual shipboard training in international vessels. They are urged to follow also the procedural assessment set by the Dutch counter part of the institution.

TABLE V
SUMMARY TABLE OF THE AVERAGE MEAN OF ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF THE RESPONDENTS

Undergraduate Colleges	Academic Performance (GWA)		
	Ave. Mean	R	Interpretation
College of Tech.&Eng'	2.11	2	
College of Arts & Sciences	2.19	3	Good
College of Education	1.99	1	
College of Maritime Education	2.29	4	Good
	2.16		

GWA Range and Description
1.00 – Outstanding/Excellent **3.41- 4.20** - Conditional
1.01- 1.8 – Very Good **4.21- 5.0** - Failed
1.81-2.60 – Good **2.61-3.40** - Average

Table V manifests that the College of Education has the highest average mean in the academic performance of all the respondents, while the College of Maritime Education has the lowest. This data shows that the pre-service teachers seemed more focused and might be engrossed with their chosen profession compared to other students from the other colleges. They seemed so concerned over their academic performance. In fact, conscious with their grades because latin honors are usually coming from this college. Further, they might have a better and positive attitude towards academic matters as well. On the other hand, respondents from the College of Maritime Education have the lowest grade among the entire respondents due to the fact that their course is not only mentally challenging, but highly technical in nature. In both marine transportation and marine Eng'g courses, students need also to be adept with computerized command and automation on

vessel manoeuvres and engine watch. Very importantly, is the passing percentage rating of all their subjects is at 60% while the rest of the colleges have only 50%. So it's not a surprise if among the respondents the CoMED may have the lowest average mean grade. However still, in plurality the respondents' academic performance is **good**.

TABLE VI
CORRELATION BETWEEN EI COMPONENTS AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF CoTE STUDENTS

EI Components	Academic Performance		
	r-value	Degree of Correlation	Interpretation
Emotional Literacy	0.043	negligible	NS
Emotional Quotient Competence	0.580	strong* correlation	significant
Values & Beliefs	0.066	negligible	NS
Emotional Quotient Outcomes	0.022	negligible	NS

*Significant @ 0.05 Crit .value = 0.232

B. EI Components and Academic Performance of Respondents per College

Table VI illustrates that in the EI components, *emotional quotient competence* (r 0.580) has a strong degree of correlation with their academic performance which is greater than the critical value ($c.v.$ 0.232) at 0.05 level of significance. Since *emotional quotient competence* is considered as the self-regulation, management and the ability to address situations, this result implies that students have difficulty in addressing some challenging situations related to their academic pursuits. At any rate, students will experience frustrations and failures along the way in achieving their academic goals, so, this achievement depends on the strength of fortitude to control their negative thoughts and feelings. If they are able to control and regulate their emotions, they will most likely achieve their academic goals as well [12]. A similar study was conducted many years ago by [14] to find out the emotional intelligence among four-year old children. It was found out that those children who have control of their impulses are better academic achievers with good social skills when they are in their adolescence stage [13] because they have better EI level.

CoTE students might have the tendency to easily give up or feel discouraged when faced with difficult situation related to their studies and would leave undone tasks. This might manifest a low academic performance among the respondents.

Reference [11] suggests that better academic outcomes might be achieved by targeting skills relating to emotional management and problem-focused coping. In conclusion, in order for these CoTE students to improve their academic performance, enhancement of their EI competencies must be looked into seriously.

Table VII is the group of respondents from CAS considered to have high EI, in fact, the highest among the entire respondents of this study (see Table II). It can be gleaned from the table that the computed r -value, when emotional literacy is correlated with academic performance has a p value of 0.278 which is greater than the *critical value*, 0.250 at 0.05 level of significance. It is then evident that there is a significant relationship between *emotional literacy* component and their

academic performance. A slight correlation between them is also observed.

The result is related with the study conducted by [5] of a period of 60 years to more than 1000 people. He found out that those who have a high IQ from childhood until the time they retire. It was found that those who acquire self-awareness and confidence during the first year were more successful in their careers. Since emotional literacy or otherwise known as self-awareness is the first dimension/pillar of EI, this should not be neglected. It is considered as the initial stage of a possible EI development once catered so that other EI dimensions/pillars can easily be enhanced. Among the respondents, it is important for them to enhance it within themselves so that the other dimension/pillar could be facilitated more easily once awareness is established. Further, [6] agreed that the most critical element of a students' success is an understanding of how to learn. Students who are emotionally literate or have self-awareness and intrinsically motivated will definitely have very high academic performance.

TABLE VII
CORRELATION BETWEEN EI COMPONENTS AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF CAS STUDENTS

EI Components	Academic Performance		
	r-value	Degree of Correlation	Interpretation
Emotional Literacy	0.278	slight* correlation	significant
Emotional Quotient Competence	0.139	negligible	NS
Values & Beliefs	0.109	negligible	NS
Emotional Quotient Outcomes	0.119	negligible	NS

*Significant @ 0.05 Crit .value = 0.250

TABLE VIII
CORRELATION BETWEEN EI COMPONENTS AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF CoEd STUDENTS

EI Components	Academic Performance		
	r-value	Degree of Correlation	Interpretation
Emotional Literacy	0.262	<i>slight correlation</i>	NS
Emotional Quotient Competence	0.208	<i>slight correlation</i>	NS
Values & Beliefs	0.116	negligible	NS
Emotional Quotient Outcomes	0.184	negligible	NS

*Significant @ 0.05 Crit .value = 0.304

Table VIII presents the correlation data of the pre-service teachers from CoEd. Evidently, both the *emotional literacy* (p 0.262) and *emotional quotient competence* (0.208) are the EI components when correlated with academic performance, do not yield any significant relationship since the critical value is 0.304 at 0.05 level of significance is higher compared to the computed r -value. However, a slight degree of correlation has been manifested between the two mentioned components and their academic performance. Like in the previous discussion (Tables VII & VIII), emotional literacy or self-awareness in the EI dimension is truly important to be established first prior to the development and facilitation of the other dimension that would enhance a better emotional intelligence. Since it is the

recognition and understanding of one's emotional state as one relate and mingle with people, it necessitates the idea of solidifying it within oneself to cater other fundamental dimensions of emotional intelligence [6]. On the other hand, [6] mentioned further, *emotional quotient competence or the self- management/regulation* once developed can possibly have some benefits in the following areas; possibly reduce the difficulties faced, prevent the problem by controlling the adverse action, achieve the desired goals, prevent erosion of a performance.

Reference [1] defines an emotional 'competence' as "a learned capability based on emotional intelligence that results in outstanding performance at work", that it represents our potential for achieving mastery of specific abilities in this domain. The emotional competencies themselves represent the degree to which an individual has mastered specific, skills and abilities that build on EI and allow them greater effectiveness in the workplace [1].

TABLE IX
CORRELATION BETWEEN EI COMPONENTS AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF COMED STUDENTS

EI Components	Academic Performance		
	r-value	Degree of Correlation	Interpretation
Emotional Literacy	0.230	slight correlation*	significant
Emotional Quotient Competence	0.127	negligible	NS
Values & Beliefs	0.209	slight correlation*	NS
Emotional Quotient Outcomes	0.131	negligible	NS

*Significant @ 0.05 Crit.value = 0.217

As gleaned from table IX among CoMed students, it pictured out that the computed *r* value, when *emotional literacy and values and beliefs* are correlated with academic performance yielded a *p* 0.230 and *p* 0.209 respectively, which is greater than the *critical value*, 0.217 at 0.05 level of significance. It is then evident that there is a significant relationship between *emotional literacy* component and their academic performance. A slight correlation between them is also observed. Although both have a slight degree of correlation, Emotional Literacy is significantly correlated with academic achievement while the values and belief are not. Like the previous discussion on emotional literacy (Tables VII and VIII), it is this component that the third year college students manifested a slight relationship when correlated with academic performance. Slight correlation is evident because their emotional literacy level, among others, is closely parallel with their average grades in the academic subjects.

Conclusively, based on the data in the table, and like the other respondents, they also need to recognize and understand their initial emotional pillar to handle his/her own emotion as one adjusts to situation around him. In this, one shall have the potential to utilize self-awareness to in order to make good use of it to deal with others.

A student who is emotionally intelligent is also academically confident which may result to a better academic

performance [2], [14]. To add to it, she mentioned that psychologist found IQ with 20% influence a person's success the other 80% is on other intangible factors like emotional intelligence quotient outcomes [2]. When correlated with the respondents' academic performance, data yielded that among the four EI dimension, it is *emotional literacy* that is considered significantly correlated.

TABLE X
SUMMARY OF THE CORRELATION BETWEEN EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF THE ENTIRE RESPONDENTS

EI Components	r-value	Academic Performance	
		Degree of Correlation	Interpretation
Emotional Literacy	0.177	<i>slight correlation</i>	<i>highly significant</i>
Emotional Quotient Competence	0.073	negligible	NS
Values & Beliefs	0.117	<i>slight correlation</i>	<i>significant</i>
Emotional Quotient Outcomes	0.072	negligible	NS

Significant @ 0.05 Crit.value = 0.1129

**Significant @ 0.01 Crit. Value =0.1480

Table X depicts the summary table of collated data from previous tables showing the consolidated results of the study. Shown in the table that the *r* values of the four dimensions are the following; 0.177 for emotional literacy, 0.073 for emotional quotient competence, 0.117 for values and beliefs and finally, 0.072 for emotional quotient outcomes, respectively. When correlated with the respondents' academic performance, the data yielded that among the four EI dimension, it is the *emotional literacy* considered highly significant at 0.05 level of significance against the critical value of 0.1129 while *values and beliefs* earned a *p* value of 0.0117, likewise higher than the same critical value. In addition, the high significant relationship of variables even at 0.01 level of significance is due to samples involved in this study (265). The more respondents are involved, the more dispersed is the relationship. Importantly, it shall be noted that the academic performance correlated is inversely applied because the school's rating system (Sta.11) is considered in this study. This system indicates that the lesser the number, the higher is the rating.

Based on the final gathered correlation of the main variables, it is therefore concluded that there is a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic performance of the third year college students especially on the component, emotional literacy (self-awareness domain), because it is believed to be the *inner core or the solid rock of one's emotion*. It is necessary therefore to develop it. Such values and beliefs are so necessary to develop self-awareness of the respondents because they help identify feelings and how these affect them emotionally as well as their academic performance. This self-awareness is the key to sensitize a person's strength and weakness. This self-awareness allows one to obtain self-confidence that could be his/her vital tool for a better performance in school or his/her future field of work.

Reference [8] suggests the need to incorporate emotional intelligence training into secondary Archives education curricula, due to a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and academic achievement.

IV. RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results of the study which are as follows; the respondents' emotional intelligence in general is considered *moderate* while their academic performance is *only good*. In the four EI components, it is the *emotional literacy or self-awareness* that has a *significant correlation with academic performance*. It is recommended that the institution would try to look deeply into the consideration of the embedment/inclusion of emotional intelligence in the curriculum or courses among college students. It is the role of the institution to facilitate their understanding. It can be done if the school shall have an effective Emotional Intelligence framework or program manned by qualified and competent teachers, guidance counselors in different colleges to implement it. Reference [9] found statistically significant increase in EQi score among general management graduate level courses who completed the emotional intelligence curriculum compared with scores in the group that was not given the emotional intelligence curriculum.

It gives the idea of the need for teachers to understand that EI is necessary in bringing about successful learners in an educational setting and also to bring about successful members of the society. Teachers, guidance counselors or personnel who shall handle this must have also undergone EI training-workshop to make sure that the conduct of the activities in that framework shall be carried over meaningfully. Since emotional self-awareness (including values and beliefs) is considered as the *inner core or the solid rock of one's emotion*, it is necessary to develop it among the students because it can be one of the main sources for the enhancement of the other domains/pillars which can positively affect the other EI domains. If this shall be facilitated well, their emotional self-awareness can be heightened which in turn can also be a springboard of the other domains to be developed. Such might prepare them to venture the real world of work in their respective on-the-job training deployment and even after college. Thus, when materialize would possibly be a good predictor of their academic success in college or even after their college education.

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